

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE MAIN METHODS USED IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL
TRAINING OF SHOOTERS**

**Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova, Oxana Y. Ilyakhina, Nikolay N. Severin,
Igor N. Ozerov, Sergey N. Severin**

Belgorod Law Institute of Ministry of the Internal
of the Russian Federation named after I.D. Putilin
308024 71, Gorkogo Str., Belgorod, Russia
Katya260688@mail.ru

Abstract:

Shooting sport is a complex coordination type of sports activity, in which success depends not only largely on how much he psychologically prepared himself for the performance. And it should be noted that not only beginners, but even more shooters of the highest level are affected by various stress factors that negatively affect the result. However, achieving high results and even more records, it is impossible without taking into account psychological factors, even with excellent coordination and excellent physical readiness of the shooter. Beyond mere meaningless strength and technique there will always be something that will not allow an athlete to achieve a record result. Because further improvement is not in the physical and technical plane but in the world of thought, in the human psyche.

Since all people are different, one takes less time and effort, the other more, but the result is the same: the psyche adapts to a certain type of activity. The task of the athlete and coach to master the methods of adaptation of the psyche. Below we will look at the psychological state and various interfering factors that have to face the athlete. The enemy, as they say, you need to know in person.

Key words: sport, psychological training, shooter, athlete, shooting

Corresponding author:

Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova,
Belgorod Law Institute of Ministry of the Internal
of the Russian Federation named after I.D. Putilin
308024 71, Gorkogo Str., Belgorod, Russia
Katya260688@mail.ru

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ekaterina Y. Domrachyova et al., **The Main Methods Used In The Psychological Training of Shooters.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).

INTRODUCTION:

When speaking at, almost all athletes note that the psychological and physiological state is very different from the state in training. As a result of this, in some athletes the result improves, in others, on the contrary, it worsens. The improvement can be explained by the optimal mobilization of the body to work, but the deterioration of the result, as a rule, occurs due to overexcitation, apathy and various anxieties associated with negative experience. Deterioration of the result is the most frequent phenomenon. Most athletes in training achieve good results, but the excitement caused by the competitive environment negates all the skills developed in training. Many athletes, faced with this problem, often simply leave the sport, thinking that this problem is not solvable. Sometimes one competition even has to hear from some coaches addressed to such athletes: “Mandrzhist, there will never be any sense”; “Born to crawl - cannot fly”, etc. But this is far from the case, “mandrzhist” - this diagnosis is not final. The human psyche is trainable, like many other functions of the human body. If we began to do physical exercises, then muscles, their strength, endurance are strengthened, if we train memory, then the ability to remember improves. And to improve your condition in competitions and better mobilization you need to do your own head [1].

Purpose of the study:

In addition to shooting sports, there are many other sports and human activities where it is necessary to solve such problems and train the psyche. Moreover, the applied methods are very similar. And in shooting, and in other sports where you need to perform some exercises that require high coordination and concentration, such as golf, billiards, diving, high jumps, etc., many of the strongest athletes use such same methods. This is an autogenous training, mental reproduction of difficult situations possible in future performances, self-hypnosis, meditation. In the same way, training in the professional activities of special forces soldiers, pilots and astronauts takes place.

Excitation is the body's response to a stressful situation. Simplistically, the physiological mechanism of excitation is manifested as follows: adrenaline and norepinephrine are thrown into the blood from the adrenal glands, which constrict and expand various blood vessels, and the frequency and strength of heart contractions increase. Due to this, blood flow is redistributed and, as a result, an additional blood flow allows the muscles to be more effectively supplied with oxygen and nutrients.

RESEARCH METHODS:

In addition, the respiratory rate increases, the reaction improves, and other body functions change. Excitation in itself is an ancient and necessary mechanism for mobilizing the body, laid down in us by nature, and allowing us to more effectively use the body's reserves in the struggle for survival. If we consider the reaction of the body to stress, then the most pronounced reaction is observed primarily on the real danger, this is understandable, but in the second place in terms of influence on the psyche there is an unfamiliar or unusual environment, which we often encounter at competitions. Unknown suggests a certain danger and therefore the reaction of the body is also quite pronounced: noradrenaline and adrenaline are released into the blood in large quantities in order to be ready to fight. But during a performance in shooting competitions, this useful survival mechanism becomes a serious obstacle to achieving results. Excessive excitement narrows the volume of attention, disrupts the coordination of movements, and due to additional muscle tension, the stability of the weapon deteriorates [2].

Apathy is the opposite of excitement and is much less common in shooting sports. It is characterized by the fact that during the performance the shooter has reduced working capacity, indifference to the work performed, and a lowered concentration of attention. Heart rate and pressure are generally not much different from resting values. The deterioration of the result is mainly due to a decrease in the concentration of attention and a decreased tone of the body. The cause of apathy in most cases is caused by overexcitation before starting, overtraining, overwork, illness, as well as lack of motivation.

Anxiety and anxiety associated with negative experiences.

If agitation and apathy are more related and affect the physiological state of the body, then anxiety and anxiety is already a psychological problem. Anxiety can have specific reasons, for example: failing to perform, fear of the first or last shot, getting into time trouble, letting down a team, etc. But there are unconscious anxieties that seem to be unrelated to anything at present. This happens on the same principle as classical neuroses develop: for example, once in the past an athlete participated in competitions and during a performance he was very worried and failed. Subsequently, the situation of the competition or thoughts about the upcoming competition automatically trigger an anxiety state. The deterioration of the result is due to an additional increase in muscle tone, extraneous thoughts and anxieties that do not allow our attention to concentrate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preparation for the competition. The conditions described above, as a rule, appear when the training is incorrect or in the absence of any psychological preparation. Therefore, for a more successful performance at the competition, the athlete and the coach must begin preparations for the upcoming performance in advance. Many well-known athletes began psychological training long before the competition: the Olympic champion from a high-speed pistol Sergey Aliferenko imagined that he shoots at the Olympic Games two years before the start of the competition, the Olympic champions Artem Khadzhibekov (air rifle) and Marina Logvinenko (air pistol) started this do in about one year. Conducted psychological training in advance increases the reliability and result of the performance. After an athlete for a long time presented himself as a speaker at the Olympic Games or other competitions, the psychological state during the performance at them becomes more stable, the physiological reactions are less pronounced. And thanks to this, it is possible to show a result, sometimes even higher than in training. Everyone can remember an example of adaptation of their psyche from their experience. Remember your shooting when you first came to the shooting range. Many were quite worried. But quite a bit of time passed, and almost nothing remained of the excitement. About the same thing happens after several appearances at competitions of the same level. All this once again suggests that the psyche is trainable. In preparation for major competitions, this process is somewhat complicated: by the fact that, for example, the Olympic Games are organized only once every four years. That is the problem. No one will wait for your psyche to adapt after several appearances at the Olympics. The medal is needed precisely at these Olympic Games [3].

How can one find the opportunity to prepare for such competitions? The main tool of this technique is autogenic (mental) training. Many know about it or have heard. But how to use it and why it is needed is often not understood. In our case, autogenic training allows you to enter a person into a state in which it becomes possible to mentally simulate any situation that is impossible in the usual state. If, for example, I'll tell you now that you are flying in the spacecraft's cabin, then you won't really believe it, you will think: what kind of spacecraft is there, I'm sitting here and reading this article on psychological preparation. But it happens quite differently if, using an autogenic training, you have entered into a state of complete relaxation, close to sleep. Here it is already much easier to feel like an astronaut and the sensations of flight will be close to real. So, autogenic training gives you a chance to visit a situation in which you have never

been, and you can repeat this many times. As a result, the psyche is trained and programmed. And therefore, the more detailed, brighter you are, for example, the upcoming Olympic Games or the Championship of the country, the more confident and successful your performance at these competitions will be.

The use of autogenic training.

Autogenic training should begin long before the competition: 6-7 months or more. But if there is a shorter period, then this will also have an effect. No matter how little time is left before the competition, this time must be used. At the first stage, you need to master the basics of autogenic training. You can take almost any technique. They are mostly similar. The main goal ? completely relax and put yourself into a nap state. As a rule, it takes from a week to three. Further it is already possible to try to represent any images. At the first stage, collective training under the guidance of a trainer or psychologist gives a very good effect. But after mastering this, you need to move on to individual independent training. This is an important point. During your speech at the firing line you will be alone (alone) and you need to be able to overcome all difficulties without outside help. For a more vivid and accurate picture of the upcoming competitions, you need to collect the maximum information about the shooting range. It is advisable to visit it, if possible. But if this is not possible, then enough photographs, video materials or just a verbal description. Having such information, it is much easier to imagine yourself at this shooting range and begin to get used to the situation of this shooting range [3,4].

Next, the shooter should remember and write down on paper those moments that negatively affect his psychological state and bring him out of emotional balance. Distribute them according to the probability of occurrence and the power of influence on the psyche (see examples below). Then, given all these factors, one needs to work through them in turn, imagining that this happened during shooting at a competition, and during one lesson it is enough to work out no more than one or two. For example, in the first lesson, you just need to imagine that you arrived at the shooting range on the day of launch, this is already enough to start the heart to beat faster. But, after a few classes, you will notice that arrival at the shooting range does not affect your condition, and your heart continues to beat calmly. We can already say that there has been some adaptation to this situation, so it makes sense to move on to the next point: for example, working out the first test shot and so on on the list. Most of the time, of course, is devoted to the factors that are most likely. One of them ? this of course, a large number of hits in the "10". If you

are attuning to a high result, then the probability of a large number of “ten” is very high, and you need to be prepared for this. When modeling competitive situations, the main thing is to imagine everything so that a little excitement appears, and then, against the background of this state, represent shooting, but not just shooting, namely the muscular sensations of the correct shot. Moreover, if some kind of verbal suggestions are used, then phrases with the negation of “NOT” should not be allowed (I DO NOT FEAR, I DO NOT WORRY). Our psyche is so arranged that the negation of “NOT” is omitted, and only the words remain: I AM AFRAID, WAVE. Therefore, when suggesting, only phrases such as: “I AM SURE”, “I CONTROL”, etc., are used. After mastering the above methodology, you can proceed to a similar simulation of the situation of the competition at the time of the training or while speaking at competitions of a low level. Between shots you need to close your eyes and imagine yourself shooting, for example, in the Championship or the Cup of Russia, after which the shooter opens his eyes and tries to make the shot most correctly. It also makes sense to use another opportunity for psychological preparation. Very often, the shooter begins to think about the upcoming major competitions and there is excitement and slight panic. This is not necessary to be afraid of - on the contrary, this excitement can be used to good use. In fact, it becomes possible, without resorting to autogenous training and other tricks, to further train your psyche. At these moments, as well as during autogenous training, the shooter should scroll through the muscle model of an ideal shot and inspire confidence in himself at the achievement of a high result at the performance. Suggestion is conducted in a positive manner. Do not allow any panic feelings and sensations. The benefit of these trainings is that the psyche is training and it is being programmed to successfully complete the upcoming work.

Negative factors and ways to neutralize them.

To facilitate and simplify the understanding of the above, a survey of athletes and coaches of the Russian national shooting team was conducted. Only one question was asked: “What prevents or has ever prevented you from successfully competing in competitions?” As a result of the survey, we got such a rather big list:

Problems related to technical factors:

- Damage to weapons during firing or before firing.
- Replacing weapons or shooting clothes just before the competition.
- When shooting from airguns, he charged two bullets at once or a bullet with the back side and fired.
- Damage to a neighbor’s weapon.
- Failure of the target installation.

- Delay in the start of firing.
 - Stop shooting for an indefinite time.
 - A long road from the place of residence to the shooting range.
 - Inconvenient shooting place (little space, tilt the floor, wooden not hard floor).
 - Unsuccessful shift. For example, in some ranges during the second shift, the wind intensifies.
 - Changing the rules of the competition. The shooter found out about this at the last moment.
 - Bad weather conditions: wind, heat, or cold.
 - A random, non-aimed shot that hit far from the center.
 - Shot at a target by a neighbor or someone hits your target.
 - The shooter forgot something from the rifle clothing, sight, cartridges, front sight, etc.
- Problems associated with psychological and subjective perception:
- Before going to the start, one of the “well-wishers” intentionally or, unaware of something, said something to you that could hurt you, such as: “Why are you so pale? Are you worried, probably?”
 - Low motivation.
 - Lack of incentive to fight.
 - Fear of unsuccessful performance.
 - Time trouble or fear of getting into time trouble.
 - High responsibility.
 - Selection for larger competitions.
 - Team competitions.
 - Unmarked shots. Add a feeling of uncertainty.
 - Bad luck. A lot of 9.9 shots, for example. This can make you crazy.
 - Accurate calculation of the result of the shooting during the exercise.
 - A large number of good shots.
 - An altercation with a trainer or with someone close to you shortly before the shooting.
 - Nervous, agitated behavior of a personal trainer.
 - Careless attitude of the coach or excessive custody.
 - Judge claims for and without reason.
 - The presence of spectators.
 - Assigned love date after shooting (Presence of a loved one near the shooting place).
 - One of your main rivals is nearby.
 - The results of shooting an opponent standing nearby are visible.
 - An unpleasant shooter, standing nearby, and inadequately behaving. Smell from any of the neighbors.
 - Change of routine right before the competition.

- Extraneous obsessive thoughts that are not related to shooting (about money, work, the opposite field, etc.).
- Planned departure home or somewhere else immediately after firing (suitcase mood).
- Factors associated with health or altered physical condition:
 - Diseases. Injuries Physical overload on the eve.
 - Monthly cycles in women.
 - Did not get enough sleep or slept. Violations of the rhythm of sleep and rest.
 - Acclimatization.
 - Overtraining.
 - Reduced performance associated with malnutrition. Food poisoning. A lot of drunk water before shooting. Overeating before shooting. Alcohol drunk the day before.
 - Overheating in the sun.
 - Procedures performed the day before or immediately before the shooting (massage, physiotherapy, etc.).
 - Love dates.

Most of these negative factors do not actually represent any serious problem for achieving a high result or winning a competition [3,7]. Some of them increase excitement, and some add elements of anxiety to the general state or distract attention. Some of these factors sometimes, on the contrary, make it possible to calm down, especially if the shooter went to the line in a very excited state, and the shooting was delayed for a while, this is often enough to calm and bring oneself to an optimal state. This list is needed primarily in order for the athlete and trainer to quickly find out the cause of the unsuccessful shooting. Often a shooter can inflate a gigantic problem out of a trifle [5,6].

For example, you can focus on the fact that a neighbor sniffs or someone from the audience is talking. In fact, these things cannot objectively affect the success of your shooting, and it depends on how the person relates to this. And often the shooter does not even realize that he started himself because of such nonsense. In the last section of the list are factors that change the physiological state. Why is this done. If you are sick, poisoned or overheated in the sun, then it is quite difficult to show a good result, but the result will be worse if the athlete begins to think that this interferes with him. In this situation, you just need to stop, take a short break, check what your head is doing, and then turn your attention to more important things. To diagnose the level of arousal, it is recommended to periodically check the heart rate (heart rate). In just 2-3 starts, you will already know how many heart beats per minute will be optimal for you. And if during shooting you find that the number of strokes has increased by 10 or more strokes

compared to the norm, then it is better to stop. The simplest and most effective method to stabilize your condition is breathing exercises. Short inhalation and long-long exhalation with relaxation of the muscles of the face and hands. This technique works almost always.

The influence of previous experience.

Often an unsuccessful performance at past competitions affects the success and psychological state in the future. This happens according to the same laws as neuroses and neurotic states develop. An unsuccessful performance at a competition may leave a mark in the memory, and in the future, any competition begins to be associated with failure. Getting rid of this is not easy. It is required to rebuild your psyche. Help from an experienced trainer or psychologist is advisable. But prevention in this situation does not require much effort and has a much greater effect [8]. To reduce the negative impact of unsuccessful performances, it is necessary to analyze your performance after each competition. The analysis of firing is carried out in two directions:

the first is to clarify the causes of unsuccessful shots (purely technical, without any muscular and emotional aspects).

the second is to recall the most successful shots, especially muscle sensations. A huge role can be played here by keeping a sports diary, in which a description of the last performance must be presented in a positive way.

Here are two examples of recording the same performance in air rifle shooting:

Option number 1.

The result is terrible (93 + 94 + 93 + 95 + 95 + 99 = 569) took 37th place out of 48 people. Before the start, there was a slight anxiety and fear of unsuccessfully shooting, but there was no strong excitement. I got to the start in a normal state, but as soon as the team was announced to get ready, and then it started, there was such a strong excitement and heartbeat that I even wanted to leave the line and tell the coach that I feel bad. There was some unaccountable uncontrolled panic, I did not know what I was doing. Everything is like in a dream. Hands sweated and shook. Still this trembling in the legs. In the second series I calmed down a bit, but then it all started again. The last series turned out not bad, but it was of little use, the train left. Two of my teammates shot much better and took 3rd and 7th place. But I let them down - the team was left without a medal. And the coach did not even talk to me. The premonition of failure was not deceived by me, it all happened. I guess I can never shoot well at competitions. I think it's time to tie up with this sport.

Option number 2.

The result (93 + 94 + 93 + 95 + 95 + 99 = 569) The result is certainly not high, but nothing. You can forgive yourself, after all, there were positive moments. Got a good experience. In the first series, I could not manage to pull myself together. But after 3 episodes I measured the pulse, it turned out to be 135 beats, a bit too much. Then I remembered how my coach advised me to do breathing exercises. Inhale and long, long exhale with relaxation. Did about 10 breathing exercises. After that, it really got better. I was able to pull myself together. And the pulse dropped to 105 beats. In the future it will be necessary to use breathing exercises and control the pulse. The second problem that had to be faced: the shots far from the center, hit nine times in the "8". The main reason is targeting. He dragged on the shot very much, and instead of postponing it, he continued to aim, and as a result, at the moment of the shot, the weapon left the center. But, there were a large number of dozens. It certainly pleases, not all is lost. The last two episodes were especially good. If you consider that the fifth series started with two 8 and 9, then we can say that the remaining shots were just brilliant, for 17 shots only 1 nine. Such a change occurred due to the fact that he remembered his last training, namely, he remembered the muscular sensations of fading before a shot. I imagined that my body was filled with water, and before the shot, the water freezes. Shooting has become much easier. Stability has improved dramatically and trembling in the legs has disappeared. It is necessary at all costs to remember and consolidate this feeling of freezing water !!!

As can be seen from these two descriptions of shooting, in the first version, the athlete explains his actions very emotionally and mostly negative emotions and panic prevail. Describing the past competitions in this way, he further consolidates the feeling of failure in his memory. Thus, he practically puts an end to his future sports career. In such cases, the competition environment is often associated with a negative psychological state. And in the future, the state of excitement, anxiety and anxiety in the competition starts automatically. The second option for recording a performance is diametrically different from the first. The result of the competition is the same, only 569 points, in fact this is an unsuccessful performance. But the athlete correctly analyzed the cause of the unsuccessful shooting, without any emotional coloring. In addition, he was able to benefit by remembering the muscular sensations of the last shots. As a rule, it is this approach that helps to accumulate positive experience and, as a result, promotes sports growth. After the competition, only positive emotions should remain.

All of the above was about how to deal with excessive excitement and anxiety, but this is not always enough to win major competitions. A calm state during the performance does not guarantee that you will be maximally mobilized during the exercise and you will do everything correctly. To achieve a high result, you will also need high motivation and a desire to win.

Correct goal setting.

Now about the goal setting. It is very important to set a goal. The goals can be set in different ways. You can set the main goal to fire at everyone in your club. It will take some time, and you really will become stronger than those who surround you but, having left for competitions where athletes from different clubs and cities gather, it may turn out that your result is at the bottom of the table. You move on, set your task to become the Champion of the country, but there is sure to be some kind of "wise guy" who will set the task to make a new record and leave you with a nose. As a result, you will always be in the role of catching up. When we set goals, then, as a rule, this goal has some specific meaning. So, if we set the task of firing at a friend in our club, and this friend of yours has the best result in shooting while lying 585 points, then we thereby limit our growth to these 585 points. And even if we set the task to break the record, then here we set limits, because the record is certain points and a specific milestone. There are frequent cases when one of the athletes suddenly sets a new record that is many points higher than the previous one, and literally after that many begin to show higher results than yesterday.

Here is one example: in 1990, the record of an air rifle for men kept at 587 points, and the bulk of the leaders shot in the region of 583 - 585, and suddenly at the USSR DOSAAF Championship, Yuri Zavolodko gets 594 !!! For us it was just a hit. I wanted to give up shooting with grief, because such a high result seemed absolutely unattainable. But only a month passed and already at the USSR Championship the result of 587 points was not among the top three winners, and the level of leaders moved to 590 - 592 points. It turned out that technically many of us were already ready for better results, but there was a psychological barrier that Zavolodko broke. Therefore, if you want to achieve a high level, then you must strive for absolute perfection. At competitions you need to set the task not just to become a Champion, but to get the highest possible result. The struggle in the competition should not be aimed at a specific opponent or result, but at a struggle with oneself, with one's anxieties and weaknesses.

Of the listed means of psychological preparation, modeling of competitive conditions in training

deserves attention, which is achieved in two ways: "mental attack" and dosed physical activity.

A "mental attack" creates an increased emotional background during training: the shooters get the task, which they perform alternately (shooting "solo") with the audience (the remaining arrows become the audience). At this time, the coach loudly comments on the shooting, announces the leader, makes a forecast, etc. All this naturally causes the shooters some excitement similar to the pre-launch state [9].

The dosage of physical activity is selected individually to obtain an adequate change in physiological characteristics (heart rate, respiratory rate, etc.). Short-term changes in these indicators can be achieved: with the help of running, squats, push-ups and other physical exercises, after which part of the shooting exercise is immediately performed on the instructions of the coach. It is advisable during the psychological training in training not only to record the result, but also to monitor the shooting technique. Modeling of competitive activity allows you to teach the shooter methods of self-regulation of the state.

The psychological preparation of shooters in a training environment is built in accordance with the general plan of the training process, in which a certain time is allocated for it. So, for example, in the first half of the training camp, she is given about 10-15% of the time of every second lesson, then every lesson. By the end of the collection, this time increases to 30-50%, and in individual classes the training time is completely devoted to psychological preparation and selection for the team (control shooting).

For the implementation of tools and methods, lesson planning is needed. For this purpose, a compendium of the training session is compiled (you can model for several trainings). Psychological preparation in the training process must be carried out in the second half of the main part of the lesson. During the competition and before the start, psychological preparation includes additional activities.

To conduct offset shooting, a schedule of shooting exercises in slow shooting is made taking into account the individual preparedness of the athlete. It represents an approximate distribution of time for the execution of shots and rest after a shot and between series [8,10].

One of the most effective methods used during competitions is the installation of competitive activity, the main means of which is conversation. The conversation can be general and individual, it

is usually held by the trainer or team psychologist on the evening before the competition.

The purpose of the conversation:

- a) analyze upcoming and possible actions of the shooter;
- b) provide for unexpected situations that can cause a sharp increase in mental stress, and the alleged actions of the shooter.

In the conversation, it is necessary to remind the shooters about the correct technique for performing the exercise, about maintaining the usual pace and rhythm of shooting in the absence of interference from weather conditions or other reasons, about observing the safety measures of shooting, set them up to fight until the last shot, to make independent decisions in an unexpected situation in absence of a coach or team representative.

The main thing in the psychological preparation of this stage is the regulation of the prelaunch state. The following tools are used for this: psycho-regulating (autogenous) training, psychotherapy, massage (stimulating or soothing), electrical stimulation, special physical exercises, etc. We will dwell in more detail on the practical application of physical exercises as the most accessible to a wide range of athletes.

Special physical exercises are part of the pre-competitive workout. Its intensity depends on the prelaunch state of the athlete: if it is closer to the starting fever, then the warm-up is calmer, and, conversely, if the shooter has pre-apathy, then the warm-up is intense with sharp movements. Pre-competitive warm-up solves the following tasks: to include the nervous and muscle systems in specific work; increase the overall performance of the shooter; shorten the operating time; restore sensations of the correct technique of a shot (or series); relieve nervous tension. "

The warm-up consists of the following parts:

- 1) general exercise; exercises with and without objects, light running, walking (20 min);
- 2) a special warm-up with weapons, preferably with shots, long-term retention of weapons in production (15-20 minutes);
- 3) a warm-up that regulates the mental state: jogging, squats, push-ups - 20 times (10-15 minutes).

Supercompensation phase

The calculation of the load is made taking into account the heart rate, for example, if on the eve of the start, the heart rate was 140-150 beats / min, and physical exercises increased it to 150-160 beats / min, then after a short rest (10-15 minutes), the heart rate should be 110 -120 bpm, which corresponds to the level of combat readiness. In

addition, it is necessary to take into account the change in the level of working capacity and calculate the warm-up and the interval of rest after it so that the start of the competition (start) coincides with the onset of the supercompensation (super-recovery) phase of the shooter's performance.

The warm-up must be selected individually, taking into account the physical and technical readiness of the shooter, the time to restore his working capacity after a dosed load, and test it at the end of the pre-competition training period. Other special exercises that relieve nervous tension can be included in the warm-up: for example, take a deep breath, hold your breath for 5-6 seconds, and tighten the muscles, then exhale slowly and at the same time relax as many muscles of the whole body as possible. Repeat exercise 9-10 times.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, the psychological training of the shooter should ensure his reliable performance in the competition.

Comprehensive training of the shooter, taking into account the main factors of reliability of his psychological training, will reduce the impact of knocking factors on the functional state of the shooter and stabilize the shooting technique in competition conditions.

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